

The Motivational Power of Emotions and Habits for the Intention to Adopt an Electric Car

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Abstract: For the market introduction of more sustainable products, a thorough understanding of consumer desires and perceptions and of ways to change consumer behavior is required. This paper focuses on the role of emotions and habits in this process. The results of a study in a sample of 1202 Belgians are reported. The introduction of an electric vehicle, which is projected to be a new more sustainable transport system, is taken as a case to explore the role of emotions and habits in the adoption intention of sustainable products. The extent to which car driving habits and emotional reactions to electric cars mediate the effects on electric car buying intentions of external source constraints and car features that offer positive emotions, is studied. The results show that emotions towards the electric car largely mediate the effect of external source constraint perceptions on buying intention. Habits largely mediate the effect of positive visceral, behavioural and reflective emotional car driving experiences on the adoption intention. The role of habits and emotions is situated in a larger conceptual framework of adoption intention.

Key words: Habits, Emotional Experience, Resource Constraints, Adoption intention of an Electric Vehicle

1. Sustainable product development, a challenge for the designer

It is considered as one of the goals of our post-modern society to reach a more sustainable future [1]. One big challenge for companies will be to move consumers towards more sustainable consumption behavior. ‘Altering consumption patterns is one of humanity’s greatest challenges in the quest for environmentally sound and ‘sustainable development’ [2]. Literature as from Ehrenfeld [3] and Manzini [4] argues that a sustainable future is not reached by diminishing ‘unsustainability’. Instead they claim that sustainability requires a radical change in thinking and being in the world and that the key question becomes how to attain ‘sustainable well-being’. In this paper we will attempt to enrich approaches towards the conceptualization of the adoption process of new products. This will be illustrated by zooming into the field of personal mobility and more specifically the factors affecting the adoption of electric vehicles. What will make or break the successful introduction of electric mobility in the real world is consumer acceptance [5]. From the literature, we know that technological innovations, in particular those needing major infrastructure changes, which is the case for the electric vehicle,

tend to fail because of lack of acceptance, unless the benefits to the consumer outweigh the costs [6]. Therefore insights into the impact of motivations and barriers of this acceptance are important knowledge for a successful introduction of the electric car. This paper zooms in on the role of car driving habits and emotions towards the electric car in the adoption intention.

2. The motivational power of Emotions

To understand the perceptions and preferences of consumers and the adoption of new products, electric car designers need to gain insight into the emotional responses elicited by products [7]. Psychological aspects of ergonomics have become increasingly important in the pursuit of products that are not only safe and efficient, but also pleasurable to use and arousing [8]. Also Norman [9] argues that the emotional reaction to design and/or to an existing or new product may be more critical to a product's success than its practical elements. These emotions are related to the complex brain structure with three emotional processing levels [10]: *visceral, behavioral and reflective*. The first level, i.e. visceral affect, is perception-based and relates to visceral aspects that are related to product appearance. The second level, i.e. behavioral emotion, is expectation-based and corresponds with behavioral aspects that have to do with the pleasure and effectiveness of use. The third level i.e. reflective emotion is intellectually based and corresponds with reflective dimensions that are concerned with self-image, personal satisfaction and memories. Emotions can play a role at different levels of the intention process. More positive emotions towards the electric car can have a positive effect on the intention to adopt it. However, perceived external source constraints or facilitators with respect to using the electric car can generate negative emotions that, in turn, inhibit the adoption intention. Further in this paper we will explore the mediating role of emotions towards electric cars for the relationship between perceived external constraints and adoption intention.

3. The role of habits

It seems plausible to assume that travel mode choices are not always taken in a rational way. They can be characterized as more unconscious and habitual, especially when we have used the same travel mode to reach the same goal repeatedly in the past [11-14]. The potential influence of habits on these decisions is very high [15]. Thought leaders on sustainability [3-4] postulate that a lot of our 'unsustainable' behavior is due to this 'unconsciousness', which is installed by repetition of a behavior that after a while becomes a habit [16]. Breaking through the unconsciousness- a similar idea of what Lewin [17] described as 'unfreezing' habits - can be a key to enter more sustainable behavior patterns.

In general, it could be expected that positive emotions related to the habitual product experience will reinforce the habit and inhibit people to adopt a new travel mode, such as the electric car. These positive emotions can be triggered at three levels of a product stimulus as proposed by Desmet [18], in line with the processing levels of Norman [9]: the product itself, the behavior related to product use and the consequences of the product. This idea is also in line with reflections of thought leaders as Ehrenfeld [3] and Manzini [4] who postulate that habit formation should be dealt with by adapting the design process and offering a better product experience. Further in this paper, we will explore to what extent car driving habits and the positive emotions associated with it, play a role in diminishing the intention to adopt the electric car.

4. Research questions

These reflections lead us to the main research questions of this study:

RQ1: Which external constraints and facilitators have an effect on the intention to adopt the electric car?

RQ2: What is the role of the emotional reaction towards the electric car as a mediator between constraints and facilitators on the one hand and adoption intention on the other?

RQ3: Do visceral, behavioral and reflective emotions related to car driving have an effect on the intention to adopt the electric car?

RQ4: What is the role of the car driving habit as a mediator between emotions related to car driving and adoption intention?

In an earlier explorative qualitative investigation, the relevance of habits and of various levels of emotions was studied [19,20]. The habit component seemed appropriate as it was felt as a barrier for the respondent to reconsider travel mode choices and driving behavior in their daily routine. Emotions showed to be important to consider at different processing levels. Driving an electric car during a simulation test elicited emotions which relate to the *behavioral processing* level. The first emotional reactions to the car (product stimulus) were captured in the facial expressions of the respondents when first confronted with the car, in the way they listened to the sound of the closing door, in the way they installed themselves into the seat of the car, etc, and also in some verbal expressions. These are more on the visceral processing level. The consequences of the electric car, the most elaborated *reflective processed emotions* came up a lot during the discussion. The qualitative research supported the relevance of habits, different types of emotions and the importance of external source constraints, and provided us with criteria and items that were then used in the main study.

5. Method

5.1. Procedure and respondents

In December 2009 an online survey was set up to investigate the adoption process of the electric car. In this paper we only highlight some of the data on the role of emotions and habits for the adoption of the electric car. Data were gathered via the snowball method. Sixty students were mailed and asked to complete the questionnaire and to forward the link also to their friends, parents and neighbors. The latter were invited to mail the survey again to their friends and colleagues. The survey was also placed on an internet forum about car driving. In total, 1202 valid and complete surveys are used in this study. The respondents all have a driver's license, 57.3% are male. The sample over represents younger people (52.5% are between 19 and 25 years old).

5.2. Measures

The *adoption intention* was measured by means of a 3 item 5 point Likert scale [21]: *I have the intention to drive an electric car in the near future; I shall recommend the use of the electric car to other people; I expect that I will be driving an electric car in the near future*. All items load on one factor and Cronbach alpha is 0.875. Car driving habit was measured by means of a 6 item, 5 point Likert scale adapted from Verplanken and Orbell [22]: *Not using the car is something that makes me feel weird; Using the car is something I do automatically; Using the car is something I do without thinking; Using the car is something that belongs to my daily routine; Using the*

car is something that is typically 'me'; Using the car is something I have no need to think about doing. Again, all items load on one factor and Cronbach alpha is 0.910. The *emotions towards an electric car* were measured using a 4 item 5 point Likert scale as used by Cauberghe and De Pelsmacker [21]: *I will like driving an electric car; I look forward to drive an electric car; Driving an electric car could frustrate me; Driving an electric car will be boring.* Also these items represent one factor and the Cronbach alpha of this scale is 0.843. The scores on the items of each variable were averaged and these mean scores were used in further analysis.

Ten items representing ten potential external facilitators and source constraints were generated from the qualitative research: *'My budget is sufficient to buy me an electric car', 'Charging the battery is possible with an electric socket', 'The car with the combustion engine will soon not be allowed to enter the city', 'The electric car can be used for long distance's, 'Not everyone can charge the electric car at home', 'Our society offers opportunities and facilitate driving an electric car', 'The costs going together with driving an electric car are acceptable', 'The maintenance of the electric car is well organized', 'Within a certain time, one will not be allowed to charge the car with self generated energy', 'Charging the battery is possible while one is on the road'.* These 10 items were measured on 5 point Likert scales. A principal component analysis revealed no clear pattern that would allow constructing a more limited number of factors. Therefore, the ten external facilitator and constraint variables were used as separate variables in further analysis.

The three levels related to car driving emotions were measured by means of 17 items that were taken from the qualitative research. We asked respondents to what extent 17 different car features contributed to positive emotions towards car driving (5 point Likert scale). Principal component analysis reveals that these emotions represent the three process levels proposed by Norman. They are defined by the following items:

Factor 1 (visceral product level emotions): *'Throb of the engine'; 'Rapid acceleration'; 'Information on the dashboard'; 'The beauty of the interior'; 'The looks of the car'; 'High speed possibility'* (Cronbach alpha: 0.880)

Factor 2 (behavioral product level emotions): *'Enjoying the environment while driving'; 'Getting relaxed while driving'*. (Cronbach alfa: 0.738).

Factor 3 (reflective product level): *'Low cost of the car'; 'Environmentally friendly car'; 'Economic consumption of the car.'* (Cronbach alfa: 0.856).

The scores on the items of each factor were averaged and these mean scores were used in further analysis.

6. Results

6.1. External constraints and facilitators, emotions towards the electric car, and adoption intention

In the first analysis, the mediating effect of emotions towards the electric car on the relationship between external facilitators and source constraints on the one hand and the adoption intention of the electric car on the other, is investigated (RQ1 and RQ2). Baron and Kenny [23] propose a standard procedure for testing mediation. This procedure consists of three successive regression models In Model 1 we test the direct effect of the independent variables (external facilitators and source constraints) on the outcome variable (adoption intention). In Model 2, we test the effect of the independent variables (facilitators and source constraints) on the potential mediator or intervening variable (emotions towards the electric car). Finally, in Model 3, we simultaneously

estimate the effects of both the independent variables (facilitators and constraints) and the mediator (emotions towards the electric car) on the outcome variable (adoption intention). In Model 3, if the mediator has a significant effect on the outcome variable and the impact of the independent variable disappears or is reduced, the effect of the independent variable on the outcome variable is fully or partly mediated by the mediator.

The results of step 1 (table 1) show that especially the constraint ‘not being allowed to enter the city in a combustion engine car’, and also the facilitator ‘being able to charge the electric car with an electric socket’ significantly drive the adoption intention. The results of step 2 (table 2) illustrate that facilitators and constraints are very important in shaping emotions towards the electric car. The biggest positive influence is the fear that the car with a combustion engine might not longer be allowed to enter the city. Also the fear of not longer being allowed to charge the car with self generated energy is a significant shaper for a negative emotion towards the electric car. Other items resulting in positive emotions on a less significant ($p < 0.5$) level are: the fact that the electric car could be used for long distances, the possibility of charging the car with an electric socket, the perceived acceptability of the costs involved in driving an electric car, and the fact that not everyone can charge its car at home. Finally, the results of step 3 (table 3) show that the emotion towards the electric car partly but very significantly mediates the effect of facilitators and constraints on the adoption intention. The explanatory power of the model predicting the adoption intention increases substantially as a result of including the emotion variable in the equation. This variable is by far the most important predictor of the adoption intention. In other words, perceived external factors have an impact on the adoption intention through their effect on the felt emotions. This clearly illustrates the importance of emotions on the adoption decision.

Table 1: Step 1: External facilitators and source constraints predicting the adoption intention of the electric car

	Beta	t-value	Sign.
<i>My budget is sufficient to buy me an electric car</i>	-.005	-.180	.857
<i>Charging the electric car is possible with an electric socket</i>	.094	3.041	.002
<i>The car with a combustion engine will soon not be allowed to enter the city</i>	.149	5.112	<.001
<i>The electric car can be used for long distances</i>	.048	1.600	.110
<i>Not everyone can charge its electric car at home</i>	.058	1.899	.058
<i>Our society offers opportunities and facilitates driving an electric car</i>	-.043	-1.370	.171
<i>The costs going together with driving an electric car are acceptable</i>	.053	1.664	.096
<i>The maintenance of the electric car is well organized.</i>	.052	1.621	.105
<i>Within a certain time, one will not be allowed to charge the car with self generated energy</i>	-.046	-1.605	.109
<i>Charging the battery is not possible while one is on the road</i>	-.040	-1.395	.163

Dependent: adoption intention of electric car. $F(10, 1191) = 7.207$, $p < .001$. $R^2 = .059$.

Table 2: Step 2: External facilitators and source constraints predicting the emotions towards the electric car

	Beta	t-value	Sign.
<i>My budget is sufficient to buy me an electric car</i>	-.049	-1.707	.088
<i>Charging the electric car is possible with an electric socket</i>	.067	2.171	.030

<i>The car with a combustion engine will soon not be allowed to enter the city</i>	.134	4.588	<.001
<i>The electric car can be used for long distances</i>	.063	2.113	.035
<i>Not everyone can charge its electric car at home</i>	.068	2.237	.025
<i>Our society offers opportunities and facilitates driving an electric car</i>	-.017	-.553	.580
<i>The costs going together with driving an electric car are acceptable</i>	.064	2.007	.045
<i>The maintenance of the electric car is well organized.</i>	.013	.410	.682
<i>Within a certain time, one will not be allowed to charge the car with self generated energy</i>	-.108	-3.752	<.001
<i>Charging the battery is not possible while one is on the road</i>	-.045	-1.579	.115

Dependent: emotions towards the electric car. $F(10, 1191) = 7.599, p < .001. R^2 = .060.$

Table 3 : Step 3: External facilitators and source constraints and emotions towards the electric car predicting the adoption intention of the electric car.

	Beta	T toets	Sign.
<i>My budget is sufficient to buy me an electric car</i>	.022	.915	.360
<i>Charging the electric car is possible with an electric socket</i>	.057	2.204	.028
<i>The car with a combustion engine will soon not be allowed to enter the city</i>	.075	3.063	.002
<i>The electric car can be used for long distances</i>	.013	.517	.606
<i>Not everyone can charge its electric car at home</i>	.020	.793	.428
<i>Our society offers opportunities and facilitates driving an electric car</i>	-.033	-1.277	.202
<i>The costs going together with driving an electric car are acceptable</i>	.018	.664	.507
<i>The maintenance of the electric car is well organized.</i>	.045	1.673	.095
<i>Within a certain time, one will not be allowed to charge the car with self generated energy</i>	.014	.560	.576
<i>Charging the battery is not possible while one is on the road</i>	-.015	-.626	.532
<i>Emotions toward electric car</i>	.554	22.860	.000

Dependent: adoption intention of electric car. $F(11, 1190) = 56.937, p < .001. R^2 = .345$

6.2. Visceral, behavioral and reflective emotions towards car driving, habits, and adoption intention

In the second analysis, the mediating effect of car driving habits on the relationship between different types of car driving related emotions on the one hand and adoption intention of the electric car on the other, is studied (RQ1 and RQ2). Again, the Baron and Kenny [23] procedure for testing mediation is used. In Step 1 we test the direct effect of the independent variables (visceral, behavioral and reflective car driving emotions) on the outcome variable (adoption intention). In Step 2, we test the effect of the independent variables (car driving emotions) on the potential mediator or intervening variable (car driving habits). Finally, in Step 3, we simultaneously estimate the effects of both the independent variables (car driving emotions) and the mediator (car driving habits) on the outcome variable (adoption intention).

The results of step 1 (table 4) show that only reflective emotions have a significant and positive effect on adoption intention. Although visceral and behavioral car driving emotions have the expected negative effect, this effect does not reach conventional significance levels. The results of step 2 (table 5) show that all three types of emotions have an impact on car driving habits. The positive effect of visceral emotions is approximately of equal magnitude as the negative effect of reflective emotions. The positive effect of behavioral emotions is smaller, but also significant. The results of step 3 (table 6) demonstrate that car driving habits partially but relatively weakly mediate the effect of car driving emotions on the adoption intention. Adding the habits variable to the model only slightly increases its predictive power. Reflective car driving emotions still have the strongest direct positive effect on adoption intention, and habits have a weaker, but significant, negative effect on the intention to adopt the electric car. All in all, this second analysis again highlights the importance of especially reflective emotions for electric vehicle adoption. In the present study, the role of car driving habits appears to be relatively limited.

Table 4: Step 1: Visceral, behavioral and reflective car driving emotions predicting the intention to adopt the electric car

	Beta	t-value	Sign.
Visceral	-.048	-1.628	.104
Behavioral	-.045	-1.484	.138
Reflective	.296	10.444	<.001

Dependent variable: intention to adopt the electric car. $F(3, 1198)=37.229$, $p<0.001$. $R^2=.085$

Table 5: Step 2: Visceral, behavioral and reflective car driving emotions predicting car driving habits

	Beta	t-value	Significance
Visceral	.273	9.621	<.001
Behavioral	.116	4.010	<.001
Reflective	-.246	-8.985	<.001

Dependent variable: car driving habits. $F(3, 1198)=68.878$, $p<.001$. $R^2=.147$

Table 6: Step 3: Visceral, behavioral and reflective car driving emotions and car driving habits predicting the intention to adopt the electric car

	Beta	t-value	Sign.
Visceral	-0.008	-0.274	0.784
Behavioural	-0.028	-0.926	0.355
Reflective	0.260	8.976	<0.001
Habits	-0.145	-4.882	<0.001

Dependent variable: intention to adopt the electric car. $F(4, 1198)=34.415$, $p<.001$. $R^2=.103$.

7. Conclusions, discussion and future research

External facilitators and source constraints have a strong impact on the valence of the emotions about the electric car. The perception that it will not be too expensive, that it can be used for long distances, that it will be possible to recharge the car in a convenient way, and that governments might regulate the use of combustion engine cars,

are all external factors that have a significant relationship with felt emotions. These emotions about the electric car, in turn, are strongly transferred to the intention to adopt the electric car. In other words, positive emotions towards the electric car are strong predictors of the intention to adopt it. Moreover, these emotions substantially mediate the effect of external facilitators and source constraints. In other words, these external factors mainly impact the adoption intention through their effect on felt emotions. This result confirms the relevance and importance of emotions for product development and the eventual acceptance of this new product, which is in line with the conclusions from earlier research as from Hsiao and Chen [7], Jordan [8], and Norman [9].

Emotions related to car driving have a significant influence on driving habits. The model of Norman is confirmed: car driving emotions are experienced in three main dimensions: visceral, behavioral and reflective. Visceral and behavioral car feature-related emotions have a positive effect on driving habits. This is in line with our expectations of the reinforcement of habit through positive emotions with the product. Reflective emotions (based on cognitive considerations) have a negative effect on habits. Stressing the consequences of the electric car, by design tools and marketing tools, opens opportunities to break through habits which is postulated to be a key to change consumer patterns into new more sustainable consumer behavior [3-4-17].

Car driving habits mediate the effect of emotions on the electric car adoption intention only to a limited extent. Perhaps, the travel mode choice between the car with a combustion engine and the electric car are not perceived as a choice between two very different behavioral patterns. These habits have a limited negative effect on the adoption intention, while reflective car-related emotions have a much stronger positive impact on this intention. So the possible global perception of the electric car as being in line with current car driving (habit) is positive for it doesn't have a strong inhibiting effect on the adoption process. In our further research, links with the component 'perceived compatibility' can be highlighted to verify this question [24]. The result again highlights the importance of emotions related to car driving for the adoption process of a new type of car. The challenge will be to find design features that stress the emotional consequences of the electric car. In this study, the impact of habits on this process seems limited. The limitations of this study offer opportunities for further research. The present study only offers a very partial insight into the factors and the processes that lead to the adoption of the electric car. Future research should focus on including more factors and on testing more complete models in which emotions and habits play are integrated. This will offer us more insights in the role of emotions and habits in the full adoption process. In the present study, emotions are investigated in a verbal, i.e. self-reported way. We asked people to formulate their emotions towards an anticipated product. Certain types of emotions (e.g. the visceral ones) could be measured in a more valid way, for instance by means observation techniques measuring facial expressions or autonomous (psycho-physiological) reactions. More research into the role of habits is needed. What are the factors that will lead to breaking through the habits of current car use? Which types of current car use can best be replaced by the use of an electric car? This should lead to answering the question which factors lead people to consider the electric car as an alternative to the use of a more polluting one with a combustion engine in a way that such a transition is felt as contributing in a positive way to the well-being of the owners and users, and how these factors interact.

8..References

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